

Strategies for using BIM in assessment and monitoring of large steel structures. Application to a sports hall.

KHALID KUBA

Supervisors:

Maria Isabel Valente

University of Minho, ISISE, ARISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal

Abstract

Today, the incidence of buildings built in earlier decades as either attempting to adapt to new uses or beginning to show signs of age and decay is on a rise. In addition, the needs of today's time call for setting up infrastructures that can face harder conditions and withstand increasing loads. Structural Health Monitoring is a technology that integrates different sensors to assess structural assets. Building Information Modelling has proven to be a useful tool to organize and oversee all data related to projects during their design, construction, and operational phases. This research aims to explore how to integrate and manage Structural Health Monitoring systems within the BIM framework in the scope of large steel building structures.

This research is carried out through the analysis of a large roof structure that is part of the sports hall Multiusos de Guimarães. The roof structure will be assessed and monitored

to withstand additional loads from new technologies in exhibitions and musical concerts and photovoltaic panelling. Firstly a model was created in the BIM environment using the software Autodesk Revit 2024: Then, it was imported to Autodesk Robot Structural Analysis 2024 to generate the Finite Element Model. The Finite Element Model was used to emulate the roof structure before and during the load test scenario. Secondly, a load test was carried out to find the roof's current structural behaviour regarding deflections. Several sensors were deployed to acquire real-time data about the loads' effects. In the Building Information Modelling framework, sensors are connected to elements. This setup allows both sensors and monitored structural members to be viewed within the BIM platform.

The study yields two main outcomes. First, the verification of the existing roof structure of the Multiusos de Guimaraes sports hall demonstrates its capacity to withstand future expansions and additional loads. Second, the research proposes a Structural Health Monitoring plan, integrating advanced Building Information Modelling technology through the Revit platform. This plan is shown to be both feasible and practical, offering a user-friendly approach for effective implementation.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/WfFFYtWm1b4>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13902353